

Non-linearity parameter (B/A) of cycloalkanes at varying temperatures and pressures

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Abstract : Four different methods Tong and Dong, acoustical, Hartmann and Ballou relation have been employed to evaluate acoustic non-linearity parameter, B/A for four cycloalkanes viz. cyclopentane, cyclohexane, methylcyclopentane and methylcyclohexane, at different temperatures and varying pressures. A comparative study of B/A values obtained from employed methods has been made.

Keywords : Cycloalkanes, acoustic non-linearity.

B/A is used as a parameter to describe the non-linearity of the medium. It can be obtained from the distortion of finite amplitude waves and the variation of sound velocity with temperature and pressure. The non-linearity parameter plays a significant role in non-linear acoustics and its determination is of increasing interest in a number of areas ranging from under water acoustics to medical science. From the knowledge of non-linearity parameter, one can gain information about some physical properties¹⁻³ of the liquids such as internal pressure, intermolecular spacing, acoustic scattering and structural behaviour etc. in liquids and liquid mixtures.

During recent past, various workers⁴⁻¹² proposed a number of theoretical methods for estimating the non-linearity parameter (B/A) for pure liquids and liquid mixtures. Tong *et al.*¹³ proposed a simplified method for calculating the B/A values of pure organic liquids making use of Schaaff's equation¹⁴ for sound velocity. Recently, using this method, Jugan *et al.*¹⁰ and Sanguri *et al.*^{15,16} calculated B/A values of binary liquid mixtures and higher alkanes respectively. Pandey *et al.*¹⁷⁻²¹ determined B/A values of pure, binary and ternary liquid solutions. Since both temperature and pressure dependence data by means of which B/A can be calculated, are very rare. Therefore, in the present work, an attempt has been made to compute non-linearity parameter (B/A) of four cycloalkanes namely cyclopentane (I), cyclohexane (II), methylcyclopentane (III) and methylcyclohexane (IV), at varying temperatures and pressures, using acoustical²², Hartmann²³, Balou²⁴ and Tong and Dong¹³ methods. The necessary experimental data desired for the evaluation of B/A have been taken from literature²⁵.

Theoretical :

Bayer's non-linearity parameter B/A , which is a particular combination of the temperature and pressure derivatives of the ultrasonic velocity, can be expressed as²⁰

$$\frac{B}{A} = \left(\frac{2Mu^2}{V} \right) \left(\frac{d \ln u}{dp} \right)_T + \left(\frac{2Mu^2 \alpha T}{C_p} \right) \left(\frac{d \ln u}{dt} \right)_P$$

$$= 2K' - 2K(\gamma - 1) \left(1 - \frac{K'}{K} \right) = 2K - 2\gamma\Gamma'' \quad (1)$$

Data on temperature and pressure dependence of bulk modulus (Warfield 1974), (Hartmann 1975) show that $\Gamma'' = -K'$ is a negative quantity. Thus,

$$\frac{B}{A} = 2K + 2\gamma K'' \quad (2)$$

where K , K' , K'' and γ are the isobaric, isothermal, isochoric acoustical parameters and specific heat ratio respectively, and the values of all these parameters have been evaluated by the method suggested earlier²⁶.

The non-linearity parameter (B/A) is obtained by using Tong and Dong¹³ equation given by

$$\frac{B}{A} = J(0) + J(x) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where, } J(0) = \frac{\gamma - 1}{\alpha T} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } J(x) = \frac{2(3 - 2x)^2}{3(x - 1)(6 - 5x)} \quad (5)$$

Here x is real volume of molecule and given by $x = V/b$, γ is the ratio of isothermal compressibility to the adiabatic compressibility, V the molar volume, ρ the density and α

thermal expansivity and b is the van der Waals constant given by¹⁴

$$b = \frac{M}{\rho} - \frac{\gamma RT}{\rho u^2 - 2P} \left[\left(\left(\frac{M}{\gamma RT} \left(u^2 - \frac{2P}{\rho} \right) + 1 \right) \right)^{-1} \right] \quad (6)$$

Thermal expansion coefficient and isothermal compressibilities have been evaluated as²⁷

$$\alpha = \frac{75.6 \times 10^{-3}}{T^{3/2} u^{1/2} \rho^{1/2}}, \text{ K}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

$$\beta = \frac{1.71 \times 10^{-3}}{T^{3/2} u^2 \rho^{3/2}}, \text{ cm}^2 \text{ dyne}^{-1}$$

where u is in m s^{-1} and ρ in g cm^{-3} .

Adiabatic compressibility is calculated by the equation

$$\beta_s = \frac{1}{u^2 \rho} \quad (9)$$

Ultrasonic velocity in liquid is affected by intermolecular interaction. The primary assumption made is that the intermolecular potential energy is the dominant factor in determining ultrasonic velocity in liquids. It can be shown that the thermal pressure contribution to the ultrasonic velocity is negligible in comparison to the internal pressure contribution. This approach approximately predicts qualitatively accurate results, and justifies the physical basis for the measurement of ultrasonic velocity. Under these assumptions, Hartmann²¹, theoretically, derived an expression for B/A as,

$$\frac{B}{A} = 2 + \left(\frac{0.98 \times 10^4}{u} \right) \quad (10)$$

Ballou's²⁴ also proposed the following relation for computing B/A :

$$\frac{B}{A} = -0.5 + \left(\frac{1.2 \times 10^4}{u} \right) \quad (11)$$

where u is the ultrasonic velocity in m s^{-1} .

Results and discussion

The values of non-linearity parameter of four liquids viz. cyclopentane (I), cyclohexane (II), methylcyclopentane (III) and methylcyclohexane (IV), at varying temperatures and pressures have been computed using acoustical, Tong and Dong, Hartmann and Ballou methods vide eqs. (2), (3), (10) and (11) respectively. Experimental values of ultrasonic velocity and density are taken from the literature²⁵. The B/A values computed by three methods viz. acoustic, Hartmann and Ballou, decrease with increase of pressure at constant temperature, while reverse trend is found in the

case of Tong and Dong method. But with increasing temperature at constant pressure, (B/A) values show inverse trend i.e. values increase by acoustic, Hartmann and Ballou methods, while it decrease by Tong and Dong method, for all the systems. Though systems I and III show some disparity in the trend of B/A values. In system I, at temperature 313.15 K, B/A values by Tong and Dong method decrease upto a pressure of 8.99 MPa, then it start increasing with increasing pressure. At temperatures 323.15 K and 333.15 K, B/A values calculated by Tong-Dong method show similar trend with increasing pressure as shown by other methods. Similarly in system III, at temperature 323.15 K, B/A values by Tong and Dong method decrease upto a pressure of 8.82 MPa, then it increase with increasing pressure. At temperature 333.15 K, Tong and Dong method shows similar trend as obtained by other methods.

Due to the smaller contribution of the $J(0)$ term to the overall values of B/A , $J(x)$ term in eq. (3) is important, and this in turn depends on x . In fact, in the Tong-Dong method, the B/A values are highly sensitive to the values of x . It has been noticed that even small changes in values of x give very absurd values of B/A . This is mainly due to the factors $(3 - 2x)$ in the numerator and $(6 - 5x)$ in the denominator in the expression for $J(x)$. Values of x should be in the range $1.0 < x < 1.2$. In fact, good values of $J(x)$ or B/A result when x lies between 1.10 and 1.14.

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